

Intestinal microflora and nanomedicines (Review)

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With age of humans is changing species composition of bacteria in the gut . Numerous studies have shown that with age there is a reduction of the number of viable bacteria of the genus Bacteroides and increasing of proteolytic bacteria such as Fusobacterium, Propionibacterium and Clostridium, in the intestines of older people, may indicate a tendency to putrefaction of colon, mainly in gut of patients undergoing antibiotic therapy. Studies have shown that in elderly patients have a place increasing of clostridia in combination with a significant increase in species diversity , especially after antibiotic therapy . Recently, the medical practice is to apply the new generation of drugs such as nanomedicines. Nanomedicines can be used orally and intravenously . As result of oral use is a negative effect on the intestinal microflora and, especially in the elderly.

Keywords: *antibiotics, bacteria, gastrointestinal tract, probiotics, nanomedicines, synbiotics*

Introduction

With age of humans the species composition of bacteria in the gut is changing [1-4]. Changes in the composition of important subpopulations of bacteria at the species level may be explained by change of metabolic activity in the elderly [5,6].

In our days the medical practice includes the use of a new generation of drugs - nanomedicines. Nanomedicines can be used orally and intravenously. Oral administration has the advantages compared with intravenous administration. However, as a result of oral application may be negative impact on the intestinal microflora, especially in the elderly.

Age-related physiological changes in the gastro-intestinal tract of human

For the normal functioning of the gastrointestinal tract is necessary to good nutrition. Chewing dysfunction caused by tooth loss, and difficulty swallowing may lead to the use of nutritionally unbalanced food. As a result of hypochlorhydria in

stomach decreases the absorption of calcium. In addition, reducing intestinal motility causes constipations. Changes in the gastrointestinal tract affect the composition of the microflora in the colon and thereby cause changes in the intestinal bacterial population.

The intestinal microflora is essential for the health of the human. Insufficient study of age-related changes of the intestinal microflora impede for clear understanding of the impact of these changes on the microbial population. This slows down the creation of possible therapeutic strategies that could minimize or eliminate such changes [7-10].

Age-related changes of intestinal microflora

Mean total quantity anaerobic bacteria in the fecal material of older people usually remaining relatively stable, however, often were observed changes in the percentage relations of bacteria of different genera.

Numerous studies have shown that with age of human going on reduction in the number of viable bacteria of the genus *Bacteroides*. This phenomenon is explained by taking a large number of antibiotics during of the life.

Changes in the composition of important subpopulations of bacteria at the species level may be explained by change of metabolic activity in the elderly [5,6].

Increased of proteolytic bacteria such as fusobacteria, propionibacteria and clostridia in the gut of older people may indicate a tendency to putrefaction colon in patients undergoing antibiotic therapy. The genus *Clostridium* includes a heterogeneous group of microorganisms with a great variety of types of food and habitat requirements.

It has been previously observed decrease in the percentage of clostridia in the gut of young and elderly patients resulting from use of ciprofloxacin. However, many studies have shown that elderly patients there is an increase of clostridia in

combined with a significant increase in species diversity, especially after antibiotic therapy [7].

Eubacteria have complex nutritional requirements, and some members of this genus are phylogenetically related with clostridia. Were observed an increasing of clostridia in gut of elderly volunteers. Increased of quantity eubacteria may have implications for human health in connection with a possible increase of potentially harmful metabolites in the gut as a result of a variety of transformation of organic matter by microorganisms [11-16].

Furthermore material from cells *Eubacterium aerofaciens* injected intraperitoneally causes arthritis in rats. If this can occur in vivo, then these bacteria can increase the quantity of cases of arthritis in the elderly [17,18].

The publications of various authors reported an increase in the number and diversity of species of lactic acid bacteria with increasing age of the person and antibiotic therapy. The ability of lactobacilli for surviving after antibiotic treatment proves their value as probiotics, especially against antibiotic-associated diarrhea. On the other hand, the presence of multiple plasmids, transposons and of insertion of sequences from different lactobacilli could potentially provide a ways for the spread of antibiotic resistance genes in the intestinal ecosystem [10].

Bifidobacteria are among the important and beneficial species of colon. Reducing the number of bifidobacteria is one of the most significant changes in the intestine, in the old age. This reduction may reduce the immune response in the gut and increased susceptibility for gastro-intestinal infections.

It was proved that in the aging in the intestine occurs a marked increase in facultative anaerobes, especially after antibiotic treatment. Some studies have shown that a huge number of enterobacteria, streptococci, staphylococci and yeasts were found in the group of healthy elderly. Enterococci, which previously never been isolated from healthy elderly person, was found in large quantities from donors treated with antibiotics. The study of the problem of reducing the number and species diversity of many useful aerobic bacteria such as bacteroides and

bifidobacteria may help establish the cause of a violation of functionality of microflora at some older people [19,20].

Nanomedicines and probiotics

Recently, medical practice includes the use of a new generation of drugs - nanomedicines. Nanomedicines can be used orally and intravenously. Oral administration has the advantages compared with intravenous administration. However, the result of oral administration has a negative impact on the intestinal microflora, especially on the elderly.

Investigation of the composition of the microflora of the large intestine, as well as an understanding of how fast to increasing percentage of elderly people in developed countries opens up new possibilities for therapy with application beneficial bacteria or probiotics.

The first introduction to the concept of probiotics was made by Dr. Mechnikov in early 1900s, who believed that the lactic bacteria promote health and longevity. He suggested that intestinal the auto-intoxication and obtained from her substances can be neutralized by modifying the composition of the intestinal bacteria and replacing proteolytic microbes such as clostridium on the useful microorganisms. Dr. Mechnikov developed of the diet based on lactic products obtained after the fermentation of milk by the bacterium which he called "Bulgarian bacillus".

Currently, probiotics can be described as live microbial food supplements which alter the species composition and metabolic activity of the gut microflora and help to increase the immunity of the organism [21].

Conclusions

In conclusion we can say that in the intestinal microflora of people with age occurs the decline of many species diversity of beneficial microorganisms. These changes in the population of the intestinal bacteria, in the diet, and digestive

physiology, e.g., the transit time of food through the intestines, may also increase putrefaction inside the colon, and greater susceptibility to diseases such as gastroenteritis or infections caused by *Clostridium difficile*, especially following antibiotic therapy. However, required more detailed studies are needed to substantiate these arguments.

Many studies conducted on healthy elderly people showed promising of use of probiotics and synbiotics in therapy, in order to maintain the beneficial bacteria in the human gut throughout life.

The future of therapy with help of the probiotics and synbiotics depends from the promotion of scientific data accumulated in this field.

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